

THE IMPACT OF LEADERSHIP SKILLS ON THE DEVELOPMENT OF PERFORMANCE IN PETROMSILA

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Abstract

The study aimed to examine the impact of leadership skills on the development of performance in Petromsila and to achieve the objectives of the research, the researchers relied on the descriptive approach with the quality of survey and correlation, and the information was collected through a questionnaire that was distributed to a sample of (91) participants. The data were also analyzed using Statistical Analysis Software (SPSS). The study found that leadership skills in all their dimensions are practiced in Petromsila to a medium degree and that the reality of performance development in the company came to a medium degree, and there is a statistically significant impact of leadership skills in Petromsila (technical and administrative skills, human skills, intellectual skills in performance development in Petromsila), and that the dimensions of leadership skills that have the most impact on performance development in Petromsila were: intellectual skills dimension, then human skills dimension, then technical and management skills dimension. The most prominent recommendations were the need for leadership to practice leadership skills in the implementation of their work in a way that supports the development of performance in the company, and the holding of training programs for employees related to the development of individual and institutional performance, as well as increasing the empowerment of employees and their participation in decision-making, and accepting their proposals in a way that contributes to the development of the company's performance.

Keywords: Leadership Skills, Performance, Petromsila.

1. INTRODUCTION

The topic of performance development is one of the important topics in all private and public companies alike because it is related to the productivity of the company, its organizational effectiveness, on which its survival and continuity of activity depend, and its ability to face current and future changes. From this point of view, attention began to be paid to administrative directions and methods to develop performance to achieve excellence, which makes it able to achieve the goals for which it was established.

The study of leadership concepts has taken on high importance, and this interest has had multiple reasons, on top of which is the increase in the size of companies and the multiplicity of their types, and this imposes a huge demand for skill and broad knowledge through qualified leaders, on the one hand, and sound thinking that represents a mental perception that extends in areas of the horizons of thought.

The growing focus on the demand of skilled leadership has also created a demand for basic knowledge of leadership processes and technical methods, in addition to serious attention to future leaders, because each generation has its leaders, so when future leaders are selected, there are special and accurate programs to educate them and the increasing interest in their development, and hard work to refine and develop their

personalities and talents in a way that suits the requirements of the future (Al-Humaidi, 2018, 103).

Yemeni society is in dire need of leaders with diverse leadership skills that raise its motivation, and work to promote, develop, and develop its institutions in light of the very difficult and complex conditions Yemen suffers from, which have disrupted many aspects of life in it.

There is an increasing need in all societies, especially developing societies, which need leaders who can organize, build, develop, and develop formal and informal institutions to reach the riders of progress.

Messila Petroleum Exploration and Production Company (Petromsila) is a leading national company in Yemen, working in the field of oil and gas exploration and production and projects related to the energy sector, it is a national energy company that plays an important role in supporting the Yemeni national economy.

This prompted the researchers to study this topic and apply it to Petromsila, because of the importance of the developmental role required of this company, which requires it to be at the forefront, of the mechanisms used to develop performance in, and to maintain the excellence of the company in light of the challenges and accelerating changes, and this is what the current study aims at.

1.1. The Problem of the Study

Public organizations in the Republic of Yemen today face many challenges, due to changes and challenges in environmental factors, as well as problems in traditional management that are rooted, due to wrong administrative policies.

These circumstances and challenges have all been reflected in the performance of organizations at various administrative levels, which made leaders face fundamental challenges in the practice of administrative processes, as they are not solved scientifically and systematically, and radical solutions to those problems that limit the development of institutional performance, but rather temporary solutions due to the lack of clarity of the holistic vision of the solution.

The failure to adopt modern management practices that contribute to the development of scientific solutions to develop performance requires leadership aware of these challenges and variables, characterized by skills that enable them to guide employees towards high levels of performance.

Leadership skills are one of the most important pillars on which the performance development process depends, as well as the reliance of most public institutions and administrative organizations on their leadership clearly in drawing their vision and mission and setting their future goals, so the institution achieves its goals when its leadership is in direct contact with its employees and solving their problems (Amin, 2017, 202).

Due to the scarcity of local studies that dealt with the topic of performance development through attention to leadership and the leadership skills that leaders must have.

Therefore, the researchers decided to study the impact of leadership skills in performance development at Petromsila to highlight the importance of the topic and to know the impact of leadership skills in performance development.

In light of the above, and based on a review of the literature and previous studies related to the topic, the research problem can be formulated in the following main question:

What is the impact of leadership skills on the development of performance in Masila Petroleum Exploration and Production Company (Petromasila)?

The following sub-questions emerge from the main question:

- What is the level of application of leadership skills in Petromsila?
- What is the reality of Petromsila's performance?
- What is the impact of the dimensions of leadership skills (technical and administrative skills, human skills, intellectual skills) on the development of performance in Masila Petroleum Exploration and Production Company (Petromsila)?

1.2. The Importance of the Study

The importance of the study stems from several angles. It is the first study that dealt with the impact of leadership skills in all their dimensions in the development of performance in Masila Petroleum Exploration and Production Company (Petromsila) "to the knowledge of the researchers", and thus may contribute to directing the attention of researchers and those interested in this vital modern topic, and it also sheds light on the reality of leadership skills and their impact on improving performance in Petromsila.

1.3. The Objectives of the Study

The study seeks to identify the impact of leadership skills in the development of performance in Messila Petroleum Exploration and Production Company (Petromsila), and in particular, seeks to:

- Identify the level of application of leadership skills in Petromsila.
- Knowledge of the reality of performance in Petromsila Company.
- Determine the impact of leadership skills in all their dimensions (technical and administrative skills, human skills, intellectual skills) in the development of performance in Petromsila.

1.4. The Hypothesis of the Study

There is a statistically significant impact of Petromsila's leadership skills (technical and administrative skills, human skills, intellectual skills) on Petromsila's performance development. Three sub-hypotheses branch out from this hypothesis, as follows:

- There is a statistically significant impact of technical and administrative skills in the performance development of Petromsila.
- There is a statistically significant impact of human skills in the development of performance in Petromsila.
- There is a statistically significant effect of intellectual skills in the development of performance in Petromsila.

2. PREVIOUS STUDIES

Many studies dealt with leadership skills and performance development, some of which can be highlighted as follows:

The study of Al-Adwan (2023) sought to examine the impact of developing the leadership skills of public school principals in light of digital transformation skills. The research relied on the descriptive approach and field data were collected using the questionnaire. The results showed that the digital transformation of public school principals provides the necessary creative climate for the development, modernization, and sustainable professional development of principals, through which their capabilities, abilities, and leadership skills are refined.

The study of Desouky (2023) aimed to identify the effectiveness of the training program in the development of leadership skills and wisdom skills among the students of the Faculty of Education at Helwan University. The study relied on the experimental approach based on the experimental design with two groups (experimental–control), and the study concluded that there is an impact of training programs based on the theory of successful intelligence on the development of leadership capabilities.

While the study of Naif, et al., (2021) examined the relationship and impact between strategic leadership skills and organizational commitment, and the study relied on the descriptive approach, to collect field data, the questionnaire was used, and the study reached many results, the most important of which are: The presence of a positive and moral impact of leadership skills and their dimensions (technical skill, intellectual skill, human skill) on organizational commitment.

The study of Muhammad, et al., (2020) examined the impact of the dimensions of strategic leadership skills on the performance of the accredited academic staff, which should be owned by the leaders of public universities in Kurdistan to achieve excellence and sustainability. The descriptive analytical approach was used, and information was collected through the questionnaire. The results indicated that there is a positive correlation between strategic leadership skills on the one hand and the performance of the accredited academic staff on the other hand. The study of Thi Bich, and Le Thai (2019), aimed to study the effects of leadership skills on the performance of Vietnamese textile and clothing companies. The descriptive approach was used, and to collect field data, the questionnaire was used. The study reached several results, the most important of which is that leadership skills positively affect the performance of textile and clothing companies. The ranking of the most influential factors was: strategic skills, interpersonal skills, work skills, and cognitive skills.

The study of Al-Faki and Nusari (2018), aimed to identify the most prominent leadership skills in public organizations, and to pay attention to the skills and development of workers at various levels that help them solve their problems and make the right decisions for the organization. The descriptive approach was used, and to collect field data, the questionnaire was used. The results of the study showed the importance of leadership skills and their role in improving the performance of public organizations. The previous studies were used to cover the theoretical aspect of the study, to direct the researchers to some relevant sources and references through reference lists for those studies, and to review the methodology used in previous studies and data and information collection tools. This study is the first study on this topic in public organizations in Yemen, "to the best of the researchers' knowledge".

3. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORKS OF THE STUDY

In the theoretical framework, the topic of leadership skills and performance development was addressed as follows:

3.1. Leadership Skills

3.1.1. Defining Leadership

The definitions of leadership in administrative thought are many and varied and vary according to the views of researchers and their intellectual background, so leadership will be defined as follows:

Leadership is a language: leadership: is the opposite of the market: he leads the beast from in front of it and drives it from behind it. Leading from the front, and the market from behind, and in this linguistic sense is a signal that the leader's place is always at the forefront, to be a guide for the group, a guide for them, a beacon for them in the way, and an example for his followers in his behavior, so that he can reach them to the desired place, goal, or goal (Ibn Manzoor, 2007, 37-70).

Leadership is also defined as the process of influencing the activities of individuals and groups to move them administratively and guide them to achieve the goals of the organization, through effective communication and creating a spirit of creativity in individuals (Al-Sakarneh, 2010, 18). Leadership is also defined as a process through which an individual influences a group of individuals to achieve a common goal (House, 2018, 25). Leadership is also defined as the process of influencing people and directing them to achieve the specified goals (Khalil, 2013, 48).

From the above, researchers define leadership as the ability to guide employees toward achieving the company's goals by motivating, guiding, and involving them in decision-making.

3.1.2. Definition of Leadership Skills

Leadership skills are defined as the ability of the leader to perform the required tasks by transforming leadership knowledge into behavior in practical practices to achieve the required performance (Bich & Thai, 2019, 21-22), as well as leadership skills are defined as the set of skills that enable managers to effectively direct individuals and manage operations to achieve the goals of the organization (Philip & Gavrilova Aguilar, 2022, 3), and also defined as the ability of the leader to plan, communicate effectively with others, make decisions, solve problems, and spread human relations among workers, work to raise their professional and technical level through professional development (Al-Otaibi, 2019, 106). Leadership skills are also defined as the capabilities possessed by the administrative leader to perform the leadership cycle in a way that ensures the performance of the tasks assigned to him/her efficiently and effectively and includes encouraging and influencing workers to achieve the desired goals (Jabareen, 2020, 30).

Through the above, researchers define leadership skills as the acquired traits and qualities, that the leader acquires through training, experience, and practice, which are a set of technical, administrative, intellectual, and human abilities and skills so that the work is performed efficiently, effectively, quickly and accurately.

3.1.3. Importance of Leadership Skills

The interest in developing leadership skills increases the efficiency of workers, enhances performance, reduces effort, and is directed towards achieving the company's goals at the lowest cost and with high quality, future management leaders urgently need to acquire new leadership skills, commensurate with the requirements of future work (Yassin & Abdul Karim, 2023, 260).

3.1.4. Types of Leadership Skills

Leadership skills vary from leader to leader, and from company to company. The following is a presentation of the most prominent skills that a successful leader must possess, according to the opinions of a group of writers and researchers:

- **Technical Skills**

It means that the leader is proficient in his work, familiar with the work of his subordinates, knows its stages, relationships, and requirements and that he can use and analyze information and is aware and knowledgeable of the available ways and means to complete the work. The most important feature of technical and administrative skills is that they can be easily verified by the leader because they appear clear during the performance of his work, and it is characterized by high technical knowledge and the ability to analyze and simplify the procedures followed in the use of tools and technical means necessary to complete the work (Hammadi, 2013, 46).

The most prominent technical and administrative skills that a leader must have are such as strategic planning, analysis and problem-solving, decision-making, leading change, monitoring and evaluation, and crisis management.

- **Human Skills**

These are the skills that the leader possesses through his ability to deal with subordinates, coordinate efforts between them, and work in a team spirit. We find that this skill needs accuracy because the leader deals with different individuals in their qualities and culture, and this of course needs special handling. The characteristics that the leader needs here are (harmony, honesty, sincerity, good morals). The leader must be a watchdog over himself and the leader must have integrity, because these qualities that lie in the leader. Subordinates feel safe and reassured about their interests, and we can realize these characteristics of the leader through his dealings with individuals and building good relations with them, understanding their feelings and needs, giving them confidence and exchanging suggestions, and giving them room for innovation and creativity (Al-Ghazou, 2010, 106).

Humanitarian skills are practiced by leaders through building work teams and ensuring effective communication and interaction with all employees on an ongoing basis, as well as motivating them to carry out their work efficiently and effectively.

The acquisition and application of human skills is one of the most important and difficult skills because it has to do with dealing with different individuals in their culture, skills, and knowledge, and because of its association with the field of human relations is more complex and diverse, so the success of leadership is linked to building good human relations with all employees of the company and giving them confidence, and motivating them to innovate and create to ensure the success and excellence of the company.

• Intellectual Skills

Intellectual skills are the ability to deal with ideas and concepts, and a leader who possesses intellectual skills can deal with abstract ideas easily, intellectual skills are a key pillar for developing a strategic vision and plan for the organization, and intellectual skills are linked to the mental work to determine the meaning of the organization's issues or policies, that is, understanding its current situation and where it is headed (House, 2018, 74).

Intellectual skills are defined as the ability to visualize problems and collect their data, arrange relationships between factors and variables, monitor problems facing work, and the ability to analyze and reach the relationship between causes and consequences (Al-Salami, 2014, 166).

It is also defined as the ability to study, analyze, and conclude comparatively, as well as the flexibility and mental readiness to accept the ideas of others (Al-Baroudi, 2015, 35).

Leadership exercises intellectual skills by having a future vision to develop the company's performance and possesses the ability to accept the ideas of others, and the ability to read between the lines see the subtleties and small and unnoticed things, and analyze them through careful reflection on the developments of the process associated with its role and impact on the company.

Leaders' intellectual skills are essential to achieving the company's goals, so it requires them to be educated with a long-term vision, accept the ideas of others, be able to think logically, collect and analyze data, deduce practical and scientific ideas to develop the company's performance, devise and implement solutions to problems, anticipate results, and be able to act quickly in emergency problems and make decisions in them.

3.2. Performance Development

Continuous performance development is the most important thing that all companies seek because it represents the most important measure of their success, as it focuses on the outputs in which the satisfaction of the beneficiaries is measured and the company is distinguished from others.

3.2.1. Definition of Performance

Many writers and researchers have dealt with the definition of performance. Some believe that performance is: doing something, performing a specific work, or accomplishing a specific task or activity, in the sense that a person performs a behavior to achieve a specific goal, it may be satisfying a specific need, solving a problem, or planning a project.

Within the framework of the institution, performance can be defined as the valuable outputs produced by the system in the form of goods and services (Abu Al-Nasr, 2008, 74). Performance is also defined as it is the results, behavior, or activity that an individual shows during work or doing any kind of effort, and thus it is equal to the term achievement (Al-Labadi, 2015, 78). Institutional performance is defined as the ability of the institution to achieve its objectives, increase interaction and cooperation among employees, confront accelerated environmental changes, and support competitiveness to ensure the stability and excellence of the organization (Al-Ajaleen, 2023, 15).

Through the above, researchers define performance as the result or outcome of the individual's behavior of business based on the capabilities granted to him by the company, which is integrated with the objectives of the administrative units to achieve the greatest possible production at the least cost, in the least possible time, and with high quality, to ensure the achievement of the company's objectives.

3.2.2. Concepts Associated with the Concept of Performance Development

- Improving institutional performance: An integrated process that applies to planned and comprehensive activities of the institution as a whole, and is carried out following planned strategies and programs that are clear and specific in their objectives, priorities, and methods and contribute to achieving the use of human, material and technical resources available to the institution in the best possible way and practically and humanely aimed at achieving the objectives of the institution and meeting the needs of workers and customers. Performance improvement activities extend to include all aspects and dimensions of human, organizational, and environmental (Barakat, 2005, 112).
- Management development: A planned and deliberate effort aimed at developing and improving performance in government agencies by influencing the values of workers, developing their skills, and changing their behavior patterns to improve the organization's abilities to make decisions and solve problems, and create balanced relations between it and the environment through the use of behavioral sciences (Kafi, 2018, 65).
- Institutional performance development: Defined as All practices carried out by the employees of the institution to achieve its strategic and tactical objectives promptly with the least effort and with the highest efficiency and effectiveness, by making fundamental changes in the administrative thought of the institution and continuously (Sammour, 2021, 29).

3.2.3. Importance of Performance Measurement

The importance of measuring performance is highlighted, by providing a realistic picture of the current situation of the institution and continuing to implement corrective actions and development projects, which leads to the growth and development of the institution, as this leads to taking effective steps to improve efficiency and effectiveness in all aspects and provide steps for the satisfaction of beneficiaries and stakeholders, and the importance of measuring performance lies in the following:

- Measure the success of organizations in achieving their goals.
- Providing information that helps in decision-making intending to determine strategic directions.
- Detecting weaknesses in achieving goals and working to address them.
- Uncovering, leveraging, and activating strengths.
- Improving the culture of accountability and transparency in the management of institutions (Zarandi & Ford, 2015, 57).

3.2.4. Developing Performance

The basics of performance development require proper planning, continuous guidance, and evaluation of the performance of employees, practical departments, and companies as a whole, to determine the extent of progress toward achieving the company's objectives, through the following:

- Design individual and group objectives and performance standards within the action plan.
- Performance tracking.
- Evaluate performance to identify the gap between planned or targeted performance and actual performance.
- Take corrective action on an ongoing basis (Abu Al-Nasr, 2008, 74).

3.2.5. Performance Evaluation

Performance evaluation requires measuring the performance and behavior of employees during a specific and periodic time and determining their efficiency in performing their work according to the job description assigned to them and the tasks assigned to them. This is done through various performance measures to ensure fairness in evaluation and produce better results. This entails issuing decisions related to the development of the employee through his participation in training programs or decisions related to the promotion or transfer of the employee and at other times dispensing with his services. Performance evaluation seeks to achieve some goals that simultaneously contribute to the development of the performance of the individual and the company as a whole, to raise his productivity and thus raise the productivity of the company (Al-Wishi, 2013, 84).

3.2.6. Developing Performance

There are organizational and general obstacles that affect and limit the effectiveness of the performance of government agencies, which we explain as follows:

A. Organizational Constraints:

- Lack of organizational guides explaining the main tasks and competencies of each department.
- Weakness of organizational structures to keep pace with environmental variables and beneficiary needs.
- Overlapping and conflicting competencies among departments.

B. General Obstacles:

- Poor control over employees' performance of their work and daily workflow.
- The company does not have plans to train employees according to the requirements and needs of the business.
- Failure to use modern technologies in the performance of work tasks, requirements, and activities.
- Lack of executive and interpretative regulations for many systems (Al-Sakarneh, 2013, 509).

4. FIELD STUDY

The field study included a comprehensive description of the methodological steps that were followed to achieve the objectives of the study, and detailed in the following:

4.1. Methodology of the Study

The researchers relied on the descriptive approach, both survey and relational, and the information was collected from two sources as follows: Secondary sources: represented in documents, studies, books, statistics, and previous reports. Primary sources: A questionnaire was designed to collect data from the study sample.

4.2. Population and Sample

The study population consists of all 173 employees of the Petromsila Petroleum Exploration and Production Company in Amanat Al Asimah. The study sample was determined according to *Stephen* Thampson's equation, where the sample number was (119) participants. The questionnaire was distributed to the research sample, and (91) questionnaires were recovered by (77%), and all of them were valid for analysis.

4.3. Validity of the Study Tool (Questionnaire)

To verify the validity of the content, the questionnaire was presented in its initial form to a group of (6) arbitrators from university professors, to benefit from their views on the questionnaire. Structural validity was also used: By calculating the correlation coefficients between each paragraph and the total degree of the dimension to which it belongs, the results showed that all the correlation coefficients of each paragraph with its dimension are high, as the results of validity ranged between (.709**, .904**).

This indicates the strength of the internal cohesion of the paragraphs of each dimension to which they belong, which means that the questionnaire has a formative validity and a high internal consistency, and its results can be trusted, and its validity to measure what it was prepared to measure.

4.4. The Study Tool

The researchers verified the stability of the research tool through the use of Cronbach's Alpha coefficient, as the value of the dimensional stability coefficient ranged between (0.96, and 0.98), which are high values that confirm the validity of the tool for the study and analysis.

4.5. Answering the Study Questions

To answer the questions of the study, the statistical package program for the social sciences was used in analyzing the data of this study and testing its hypotheses, where the program (SPSS: ver. 26) was used. This is detailed as follows:

4.5.1. Presentation and Analysis of the Results of the Study Questions

- Answer to the first question "What is the level of application of leadership skills in Petromsila? "

To answer this question, the arithmetic mean, standard deviation, and the level of application were extracted at the level of each dimension of leadership skills, and Table (1) shows the arithmetic means, standard deviations, and the level of application of the views of the study sample.

Table 1: Responses of the Study Sample on the Dimensions of Leadership Skills

No.	Paragraphs	Order	means	Standard Deviation	Application level	Verbal connotation
1	Technical and Administrative Skills	1	3.46	0.68	69%	High
2	Human Skills	3	3.21	0.84	%64	Medium
3	Intellectual skills	2	3.24	0.82	%65	Medium
Leadership Skills			3.30	0.78	%66	Medium

It is clear from Table (1) that the general average of leadership skills in Petromsila Company amounted to (3.30), with a standard deviation of (0.78), and with an application level of (66%). This means that the level of leadership skills from the point of view of the study sample in Petromsila Company in general was (medium). The researchers attribute this result to a weakness to some extent in the leadership's practice of leadership skills in the company, especially the human skills represented in human interaction with all workers by listening to their suggestions, dealing positively with them, and motivating them to work.

It is also clear from the previous results that the arithmetic mean of the dimensions of leadership skills ranged from (3.46-3.21), where the degree of appreciation of all dimensions was (medium), and this indicates that leadership skills in all their dimensions are practiced in the company with a degree (medium), with a slight variation in the values of arithmetic means that reflected the order of each dimension in terms of priority, where the dimension of technical and administrative skills ranked first, then the dimension of intellectual skills ranked second, and then the dimension of human skills ranked third.

By analyzing the previous statistical results, it is possible to answer the first question of the study that the reality of leadership skills in Petromsila came with a grade of (Medium).

– **Answer to the second question, which reads: (What is the reality of performance in Petromsila?)**

To answer this question, the arithmetic mean, standard deviation, and the level of application were extracted at the level of each dimension of performance, and Table (2) shows the arithmetic means, standard deviations, and the level of application of the views of the study sample.

Table 2: Responses of the Study Sample to Performance

#	Paragraphs	Order	means	Standard Deviation	Application level	Verbal connotation
1	Institutional Performance	1	3.28	0.75	%66	Medium
2	Individual performance	2	2.96	0.87	59%	Medium
Performance			12.3	0.78	%62	Medium

It is clear from Table (2) that the overall average performance in Petromsila was (3.12), with a standard deviation of (0.78), and with an application level of (62%). This means that the level of performance from the point of view of the study sample in Petromsila in general was (medium). The researchers attribute this result to the existence of some weakness in performance, resulting from the lack of clear criteria for measuring performance, the lack of clarity of the functional tasks of all departments, and the low quality of production.

It is also clear from the previous results that the arithmetic means of the dimensions of leadership skills ranged between (3.28-2.96), where the degree of estimation of all dimensions was (medium), and this indicates that performance in all its dimensions is practiced in the company with a degree (medium), with a slight variation in the values of arithmetic means that reflected the ranking of each dimension in terms of priority, where the dimension of institutional performance came first, and then the dimension of individual performance in second place.

By analyzing the previous statistical results, it is possible to answer the second study question that the reality of performance in Petromsila came with a grade (medium).

4.5.2. Hypotheses Testing

In this part of the study, we review the hypothesis testing, to verify the impact of the dimensions of leadership skills on performance. The main hypothesis, reads: There is a statistically significant impact of leadership skills (technical and administrative skills, human skills, intellectual skills) in the development of performance in Petromsila. Three sub-hypotheses branch out from this hypothesis, as follows:

- The first sub-hypothesis, which reads: There is a statistically significant effect of the dimension of technical and administrative skills in the development of performance in Petromsila), and to test the sub-hypothesis, simple linear regression was used, and the results were as follows:

Table 3: Impact Test Results after Technical and Administrative Skills in Performance Development

Summary of Forms			Analysis of Variance (ANOVA)			Regression Coefficients			
Dependent Variable	(R) correlation coefficient	(R ²) coefficient of determination	(F) calculated	sig F* Significance level	df degree of freedom	Independent Variable	Value β	t	sig t* Significance level
Performance Development	0.669	0.45	72.11	0.000	1.89	Technical and administrative skills	0.76	8.49	0.00

The results of Table (3) indicate that there is a statistically significant relationship to the dimension of technical and administrative skills in performance development, as the calculated value of (F) reached (72.11) with a level of significance of (0.00), which is less than (0.05), while the correlation coefficient (R) reached (0.669), which means that there is a positive direct relationship between the dimension of technical and administrative skills and performance development. In addition, the value of the coefficient of determination was (R²=0.45), which indicates the significance of the regression. It was also found that the variation in the dimension of technical and administrative skills explains (45%) of the variation in performance development, provided that the other variables are constant.

The results of the regression analysis also showed that the value of the coefficient of determination (β) amounted to (0.76) and that the value of (t) at it is (8.49) with a significance level of (0.00), and in light of this, the hypothesis is accepted.

- The second sub-hypothesis reads: (There is a statistically significant effect of the dimension of human skills in the development of performance in Petromsila), and to test the sub-hypothesis, simple linear regression was used, and the results were as follows:

Table 4: Results of a Test of the Impact of the Dimension of Human Skills in Performance Development

Summary of Forms			Analysis of Variance (ANOVA)			Regression Coefficients			
Dependent Variable	(R) correlation coefficient	(R ²) coefficient of determination	(F) calculated	sig F* Significance level	df degree of freedom	Independent Variable	Value β	t	sig t* Significance level
Performance Development	0.80	0.65	162.46	0.00	1.89	human skills	0.84	12.75	0.00

The results of Table (4) indicate that there is a statistically significant relationship between the dimension of human skills in performance development, as the calculated value of (F) was (162.46) with a level of significance of (0.00), which is less than (0.05), while the correlation coefficient (R) was (0.80). This means that there is a positive direct relationship between the dimension of human skills and performance development, in addition to the value of the coefficient of determination ($R^2=0.65$), which indicates the significance of regression. It was also found that the variation in the dimension of human skills explains (65%) of the variation in performance development, provided that the other variables are constant.

The results of the regression analysis also showed that the value of the coefficient of determination (β) amounted to (0.84) and that the value of (t) at it is (12.75) with a significance level of (0.00), and in light of this, the hypothesis is accepted.

- The third sub-hypothesis reads: (There is a statistically significant effect of the intellectual skills dimension in the development of performance in Petromsila), and to test the sub-hypothesis, simple linear regression was used, and the results were as follows:

Table 5: Results of an Impact Test after Intellectual Skills in Performance Development

Summary of Forms			Analysis of Variance (ANOVA)			Regression Coefficients			
Dependent Variable	(R) correlation coefficient	(R ²) coefficient of determination	(F) calculated	sig F* Significance level	df degree of freedom	Independent Variable	Value β	t	sig t* Significance level
Performance Development	0.84	0.70	211.74	0.00	1.89	intellectual skills	0.89	14.55	0.00

The results of Table (5) indicate that there is a statistically significant relationship between the dimension of intellectual skills in performance development, as the calculated value of (F) was (211.74) with a level of significance of (0.00), which is less than (0.05), while the correlation coefficient was (R (0.84), which means that there is a positive direct relationship between the dimension of intellectual skills and performance development, in addition to that the value of the coefficient of determination was ($R^2=0.70$), which indicates the significance of regression, and it is also clear that the variation in the dimension of intellectual skills explains (70%) of the variation in performance development, provided that the other variables are constant.

The results of the regression analysis also showed that the value of the coefficient of determination (β) amounted to (0.89) and that the value of (t) at it is (14.55) with a significance level of (0.00), and in light of this, the hypothesis is accepted. By reviewing the results of testing the sub-hypotheses shown in tables (3), (4), and (5), the main hypothesis is accepted, which reads: There is a statistically significant effect of leadership skills (technical and administrative skills, human skills, intellectual skills) in the development of performance in Petromsila. To indicate the most influential independent variables and give the greatest explanatory power to the variables in performance development, the independent variables of the dimensions of leadership skills combined were subjected to gradual linear regression, and the results were as follows:

Table 6: Results of Graded Linear Regression Analysis of the Combined Dimensions of Leadership Skills on Performance Development

Form	Categories	Summary of Forms		Analysis of Variance			Regression model coefficients					
		(R) correlation coefficient	(R ²) coefficient of determination	(F) calculated	Significance level	Degree of freedom df	Transaction Values		T	Significance level		
1	Intellectual skills:	0.839	0.70	211.738	0.00	1.90	β	0.88	14.5	0.00		
	Constant						α	0.23			1.16	0.24
2	Intellectual skills:	0.854	0.73	118.079	0.00	1.90	β_1	0.60	5.17	0.00		
	human skills						β_2	0.33			2.82	0.00
	Constant						α	0.11			4.05	0.57

When reviewing the results of Table (6), we find the first model resulting from gradual regression, which indicates that the dimension of (intellectual skills) explains (70%) of the total variation in the development of performance in Petromsila, where the value of ((R²=0.70) and the value of ((F= 211.738) at a level of significance (0.00), which confirms the significance of regression, as evidenced by the regression coefficients that there is a statistically significant effect of the dimension of (intellectual skills), as the results showed that the value of (β) reached (0.88) and the value of (T) at it is (14.5), and at a level of significance (0.00), which indicates that the impact of this dimension is statistically significant. The second model: The result of the gradual regression indicates that the two dimensions (intellectual skills and human skills) combined in the second model explain (73%) of the total variation in the development of performance in Petromsila, where the value of (R²=0.73 (F= 118.079) with a significance level of (0.00), which confirms the significance of regression, as evidenced by the regression coefficients that there is a statistically significant effect for the two fields (intellectual skills and human skills), where the results showed that the value of (β_1, β_2) was respectively: (0.33,0.60) and that the value of (T) at it is (2.82,5.17), with a significance level of (0.00,0.00), which indicates that the impact of the fields is statistically significant, and according to the gradual regression analysis, the result of two models can be expressed in the following equations:

The first model: (intellectual skills) * β = (performance development).

The first model: (Intellectual skills) * 0.88 = (Y).

It is clear from the value of (β) (0.88), which indicates the strength or degree of influence, that is, the improvement in the "application of intellectual skills" by one

degree is followed by development in "performance" by (0.88) degrees, assuming the stability of the rest of the variables.

The second model: (intellectual skills) * β_2 + (human skills) * β_1 = (performance development).

The second model: (Intellectual Skills) * 0.60 + (Human Skills) * 0.33 = (Y).

It is clear from the value of " β_1 , β_2 " (0.60 & 0.33), which indicates the strength or degree of influence, that is, the improvement in the "application of intellectual and human skills" with one degree, followed by an improvement in performance with (0.93) degrees, assuming the stability of the rest of the variables.

5. CONCLUSION

The study showed some results, the most prominent of which are:

- The variable of leadership skills in all its dimensions is practiced in Petromsila with a medium degree according to the opinion of the study sample, with a slight variation in the values of arithmetic means that reflected the ranking of each dimension according to priority, and its ranking was as follows: (technical and administrative skills, intellectual skills, human skills).
- The performance development variable in all its dimensions is practiced in Petromsila to a medium degree, with a slight variation in the values of the arithmetic means that reflected the ranking of each dimension in terms of priority, where the dimension of institutional performance came first, and then the dimension of individual performance in second place.
- There is a statistically significant impact of Petromsila's leadership skills (technical and administrative skills, human skills, intellectual skills) in the development of Petromsila's performance, and the dimensions of leadership skills that have the most impact on the development of performance in Petromsila were: the dimension of intellectual skills, then the dimension of human skills, then the dimension of technical and administrative skills.
- There is a statistically significant impact of the dimension of technical and administrative skills in the development of performance in Petromsila, and this indicates that more attention is paid to strategic planning, the use of scientific methods in decision-making, and work on crisis management in systematic ways, this has affected the development of performance in the company.
- There is a statistically significant impact of the human skills dimension in the development of performance in Petromsila, and this indicates that the more attention is paid to team building, the availability of effective communication channels, and the diversity in employee motivation, this has positively affected the development of performance in the company.
- There is a statistically significant impact of the intellectual skills dimension in the development of performance in Petromsila, and this indicates that the more leadership has a long-term future vision, and the ability to accept and absorb the ideas of others, this has positively affected the development of performance in the company.

6. RECOMMENDATIONS

- Leadership commitment to practice leadership skills in the implementation of their work to support the development of performance in the company. Taking into account the need to prioritize the impact of the dimensions of leadership skills in performance development to obtain an effective impact of the dimensions of leadership skills in performance development.
- It is necessary for the company's leadership commitment to promote the application of leadership skills by practicing participation in strategic planning and work procedures, ensuring that employees are involved in the decision-making process, and giving them sufficient flexibility to allow them to practice their work efficiently and effectively.
- The need to pay attention to the development of human and intellectual skills in particular because of their low level compared to administrative and technical skills through the holding of specialized training courses in this field.
- Holding training and qualification programs for employees related to the development of individual and institutional performance.
- Develop administrative processes and procedures periodically and work to provide the appropriate environment for creativity and innovation.
- Increasing the empowerment of employees and their participation in decision-making, and accepting their proposals in a way that contributes to the development of the company's performance.
- Conduct further applied studies on this topic from different angles and dimensions.

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